

CONVERGENCE OF GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT AND DIGITALIZATION EFFORTS IN THE PHILIPPINES: REFLECTIONS FROM THE AQUINO III TO MARCOS JR. ADMINISTRATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12679710>

ABSTRACT

Gender mainstreaming and development efforts have long been part of the modern world's initiatives towards equality in society, and this is no different in the Philippines. The country annually devotes resources for initiatives designed to create a culture of inclusivity, equality, and opportunity for all genders. These efforts include allocating part of the annual budget for these goals and the creation of the "National Entity for Gender Equality and Women Empowerment". Likewise, the country is also expediting digitalization efforts to modernize government initiatives by improving digital connectivity through automated processes, systems, and services. Its goal is to become more responsive to emerging contexts while making government services more accessible to the public. This digitalization shall remain inclusive to all genders and will champion gender equality. At present, both goals are classified as priorities under the Marcos Jr. Administration as articulated in Philippine Development Plan (2023-2028). As such, the researchers have conducted descriptive-qualitative research; Guided by content and thematic analyses, they discussed the convergence between two equally important efforts from the Aquino III administration to the present and proposed recommendations on strengthening points for convergence.

Keywords: *Convergence, Development, Efficiency, Digitalization, Gender Mainstreaming, Transformation*

INTRODUCTION

Gender mainstreaming has been a consistent effort by countries around the world to advance gender equality. Originally introduced in 1985 during the Nairobi World Conference on Women, it was then adopted to policy in 1995 through the Beijing Platform for Action, where it was aimed at "...accelerating the implementation of the Nairobi Forward-looking Strategies for the Advancement of Women and at removing all the obstacles to women's active participation in all spheres of public and private life through a full and equal share in economic, social, cultural and political decision-making." (Fourth World Conference on Women, Beijing 1995, n.d.)

The Council of Europe of 1998 defined Gender mainstreaming as "[t]he (re)organisation, improvement, development and evaluation of policy processes, so that a gender equality perspective is incorporated in all policies at all levels and at all stages, by the actors normally involved in policy-making." (What Is Gender Mainstreaming? - Gender Equality - www.coe.int, n.d.) To put it simply, gender mainstreaming factors in the separate needs and collective wellbeing of both men and women in relation to resources, living conditions, human rights, and access to services and institutions. It requires institutional reforms as well as changes in culture, perception, and practices.

However, gender mainstreaming efforts in the Philippines began even before the term was officially coined. On January 7, 1975, then - President Ferdinand E. Marcos Sr. instituted the National Commission on the Role of Filipino Women (NCRFW) by virtue of Presidential Decree No. 633 (Aliliran, 2022). The Commission's main role was to "review, evaluate and recommend measures, including priorities to ensure the full integration of women for economic, social and cultural development at the national, regional and international levels and to ensure further equality between men and women." (Presidential Decree No. 633, 1975).

From 1975 to 1986, the NCRFW directed its efforts towards the elimination of discriminatory provisions within Philippine law. This is in line with the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women, which was ratified in 1981. Additionally, under the program of action set forth under the UN Decade for Women, which lasted from 1975 to 1985, the "Balikatan Sa Kaunlaran" was established. This was a "nationwide movement" that focused on "creating opportunities for expanded roles of women in economic, social and political activities of the nation." (Making Government Work for Women's Empowerment and Gender Equity, 2000). Its programs predominantly covered initiatives related to livelihood, leadership, and income generation opportunities for women throughout the country. The movement was incorporated by the NCRFW and continues to be involved in initiatives that focus on the social and economic endeavors of women today.

Moreover, it was during Marcos, Sr.'s administration when the country became the first ASEAN country to adopt the Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), also known as the International Bill of Rights of Women. It was signed on July 15, 1980, and officially ratified on August 5 of the

following year. It is identified as “an international legal instrument that requires countries to eliminate discrimination against women and girls in all areas and promotes women’s and girls’ equal rights.” (Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) for Youth, 2013).

In the years following the 1986 EDSA People Power Revolution, gender mainstreaming officially entered the landscape of Philippine politics under President Corazon C. Aquino's administration. Article II, Section 14 of the 1987 Constitution “recognizes the role of women in nation-building, and shall ensure the fundamental equality before the law of women and men.” (1987 Philippine Constitution, Article II, Section 14). During this period, equality-centric policies were adopted, including the Philippine Development Plan for Women (PDPW) from 1989 to 1992, established through Executive Order 348 (Executive Order No. 348, 1989). The PDPW focused on implementing projects and measures that addressed women's socio-economic needs, calling upon government agencies to oversee the implementation and monitoring of these initiatives.

Gender mainstreaming efforts in the Philippines continued after the PDPW's expiration in 1992 with the enactment of Executive Order 273, which served as the main avenue for the country's application of the Beijing Platform for Action. The order aimed to implement the directives outlined in President Fidel V. Ramos' Philippine Plan for Gender-Responsive Development, 1995-2025, which included the institutionalization of Gender and Development (GAD) initiatives. Like the PDPW, the Plan mandated government offices to incorporate GAD concerns in their planning, programming, and budgeting processes. (Executive Order No. 273, 1995). It also tasked the NCRFW to collaborate with the National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA) in assessing implementation efforts and making necessary adjustments to the Plan's provisions every six years. These efforts were further enhanced during former President Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo's administration through the enactment of Republic Act. 9710, otherwise known as the “Magna Carta for Women” in 2009. (Republic Act No. 9710, 2009), which continues to be a guiding beacon for GAD initiatives of succeeding administrations.

More than two decades later, the Philippines continues to preserve and support women's socio-economic well-being through the Philippine Development Plan (PDP) 2023-2028. Drawing from the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, the administration of President Ferdinand "Bongbong" Marcos, Jr. has oriented the PDP towards strengthening social protection systems for vulnerable groups, including women and children. The plan also aims to ensure that marginalized sectors, such as women, children, indigenous peoples, and persons with disabilities, have concrete roles and significant influence in all stages of public decision-making. (National Economic Development Authority, 2023).

Furthermore, the PDP partly focuses on strengthening "social cohesion" by establishing gender-responsive intervention systems, encouraging community participation, and safeguarding the welfare of women and other vulnerable groups,

including the LGBTQIA community. It also seeks to reinforce the implementation of laws that protect women, such as the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act of 2004, Safe Spaces Act, Anti-Trafficking in Persons Act of 2003, Anti-Mail Order Spouse Act, and the Domestic Workers Act or Batas Kasambahay. (National Economic Development Authority, 2023).

Parallel to the illustrious history of gender mainstreaming efforts in the country is the pursuit of digitalization. In their book titled “Action Fields of Digital Transformation - A Review and Comparative Analysis of Digital Transformation Maturity Models and Frameworks,” Bumman and Peter (2019) consolidate and differentiate digitalization from other associated terms, such as digitization and digital transformation. To summarize, using an Input-Process-Output Model, digitization is associated with input, wherein analog data (words, speech, recordings, etc.) are converted to digital data. Digitalization (process) refers to the shift from manual processing to digital, such as online appointments and bookings. Finally, digital transformation (output) involves the mainstreaming of created online platforms and businesses into society, such as online shopping platforms, digital currency, and artificial intelligence. (Bumann & Peter, 2019).

Like GAD, the origins of digitalization efforts in the Philippines can be traced back to the Marcos Sr. administration when the National Computer Center was created through Executive Order No. 322 in 1971. Under this EO, Electronic Data Processing (EDP) was to be integrated across government agencies' operations and inform government planning, research, and engineering. (Executive Order No. 322, 1971). The NCC was later restructured seven years after its establishment by virtue of Presidential Decree 1480 of 1978.

Despite the political turmoil of that era, digitalization efforts were carried out by the Aquino administration. Article II of the 1987 Constitution emphasizes the vital role of communication and information in nation-building. (1987 Philippine Constitution, Article II, Section 24). The administration focused on rebuilding a democratic government through ICT to improve transparency, accountability, and citizen engagement.

The Ramos administration continued these efforts through emphasis on telecommunications expansion and its importance in economic development and security through Republic Act 7925, also known as the Telecommunications Policy Act of 1995 (Republic Act No. 7925, 1995). Additionally, the National Information Technology Plan for the 21st Century (IT21) was launched in 1997 under his administration, highlighting the country's shared vision and strategy in spurring global competitiveness through Information Technology (National Information Technology Plan for the 21st Century (IT21), n.d.).

Then President Joseph Ejercito “Erap” Estrada sustained the momentum of digitalization and e-government initiatives by establishing the e-Philippines Strategy Government Information Systems Plan and creating the Information Technology and Electronic Commerce Council (ITECC) by virtue of Executive Order No. 264, s. 2000. (Executive Order No. 264, 2000).

This was followed by the Philippine Strategic ICT Roadmap and the Philippine Digital Strategy created under Presidents Gloria Macapagal Arroyo and Benigno "Noy" Aquino III, respectively. The Arroyo administration pushed for digital inclusion and literacy, as well as the institutionalization of e-government funds and the diffusion of information and communications technology. (Gurumurthy et al., 2016).

Specifically, the Aquino administration collaborated with the National IT Industry Promotion Agency (NIPA) from South Korea to launch the Philippine e-Government Master Plan. The plan aimed to build a blueprint for future e-Government initiatives that would lead to innovation in government work processes, better public services for businesses and citizens, and the promotion of citizen participation. (National Computer Center & National IT Industry Promotion Agency, 2012).

Meanwhile, digitalization, in the context of the Duterte Administration emphasizes addressing red tape on government bureaucracy through the enactment of Republic Act 11032, otherwise known as the "Ease of Doing Business (EODB)" Law of 2018. Under said act entailed the streamlining of government systems and processes, allowing a more efficient delivery of services to the people. Moreover, this law officially amends the Republic Act 9485 or the Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007. (Republic Act No. 11032, 2018).

On January 2021, the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT) and the Anti-Red Tape Authority (ARTA) launched the first phase of the Central Business Portal (CBP), a platform where citizens and business owners can access forms and requirements necessary for business registration. (Crismundo, 2021).

For its part, the Marcos Jr. Administration seeks to build robust data systems to create better programs, such as targeted social protection and more efficient employment-opportunity linking systems. (National Economic Development Authority, 2023). These goals are part of the administration's 8-Point Socioeconomic Agenda, with PHP15.6 billion out of the 2023 National Budget allocated to facilitate the transformation and digitalization of the whole-of-government, aligning with the Marcos Jr. Administration's thrust for a lean, efficient, and responsive government workforce. (GAA 2023 Starting Point for Marcos Jr. Administration's 8-Point Socioeconomic Agenda, n.d.).

Research Questions

Reflecting from reviewed literature from the Aquino III administration to the Marcos Jr. administration, the study aims to answer the question: What are the current gender mainstreaming initiatives and digitalization efforts that are being implemented by the Philippine government?

Further, through thematic analysis, the study seeks to answer the following:

- 1) Are there any efforts launched by the government that integrate both Gender and Development (GAD) and digitalization (whether processes or actual programs / projects)?
- 2) What are the strong points of previous and/or current efforts by the government?
- 3) What are the perceived limitations and documented gaps of said efforts?
- 4) What are the recommended strategies or adjustments that the Philippine government can employ to facilitate improvement both on ongoing efforts and proposed to be created and/or reinstated initiatives?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers used qualitative-descriptive research approaches. According to Bhandari (2023), Qualitative Research is “involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data (e.g., text, video, or audio) to understand concepts, opinions, or experiences”. (Bhandari, 2023). Conversely, Descriptive Research seeks to describe accurately and systematically a population, situation or phenomenon (McCombes, 2023). The abstract is founded on the premise that GAD and digitalization efforts shall be discussed, as well as instances they converge. Hence, the above-mentioned methods were determined to be the most appropriate for this study.

Additionally, to fully understand the literature selected and establish a sound basis for findings and recommendations, the researchers primarily utilized context analysis tool. As defined, it is the “utilization of specific words, themes or concepts in some given qualitative data (texts)”. (Content Analysis Method and Examples | Columbia Public Health, 2023). Furthermore, thematic analysis was employed by the researchers for enhanced depth and brevity. As described, it is “a way of identifying patterns (themes) across a dataset which can be used for subsequent analysis”. (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis is effective in grouping recurring themes across different literatures while avoiding any tendencies towards confirmation biases.

It should be noted that this study will only cover major GAD and digitalization efforts implemented, currently being implemented and/or pipelined for implementation by the Philippine government. Hence, similar interventions from the private sector or non-governmental organizations will not be considered unless it is a joint effort with the government. Moreover, the convergence of GAD and digitalization efforts mentioned are only those adopted by the entire or at least the majority of the government bureaucracy. Hence, agency-specific convergence efforts will not be taken into account. Period coverage will focus on the Aquino III up to the Marcos Jr. administration. However, relevant historical antecedents about preceding administrations were occasionally cited to establish context.

RESULTS

Based on literature review conducted by the researchers, the following themes were identified with regard to the GAD and Digitalization efforts during the Aquino III to the Marcos Jr. administration as follows:

Table 1

Summary of Themes

THEME	DESCRIPTION
DIGITAL ECONOMY	Digital economy, as defined, refers to that “part of economic output derived solely or primarily from digital technologies with a business model based on digital goods or services.” (Bukht & Heeks, 2017). In its simplest sense, both manufacturers and consumers in this economy utilize the internet and various electronic platforms to manage, market, and purchase goods and services. In return, this improves business efficiency through cost reduction, deviation from excessive manual labor, minimization of errors, and overall speed enhancement.
BUREAUCRATIC EFFICIENCY	As defined, Bureaucracy is the “specific form of organization defined by complexity, division of labor, permanence, professional management, hierarchical coordination and control, strict chain of command, and legal authority.” (Rockman, 1998). On the other hand, efficiency is defined as the “state or quality of being efficient, or able to accomplish something with the least waste of time and effort”. (“Dictionary.com Meanings & Definitions of English Words,” 2020). Hence, in the context of governance, bureaucratic efficiency can be defined as the ability of a government institution [or government at large] to operate and facilitate the delivery of its programs and services within their prescribed period and with minimal resources utilized.
CONVERGENCE	<p>In its simplest terms, it is defined as the “act of converging and especially moving toward union or uniformity.” (“Convergence,” 2024). In the context of information communications technology (ICT), it is the “integration of two or more different technologies in a single device or system.” (Rouse, 2023). In the context of project implementation, it can be defined as different project elements coming together to facilitate a shared outcome and/or impact.</p> <p>For this study, converge refers to the efforts wherein GAD and Digitalization are integrated into one geared towards different, but complementary goals.</p>

DISCUSSION

Digital Economy

It is no secret that the internet, cloud computing, and the availability of electronic devices have been facilitating growth in the digital economy. They have revolutionized how business operates and expand its operations – creating new avenues to market products and services, as well as attracting potential clients and investors. It is posited that “Digital technologies and their attendant applications are reshaping whole domains of human activity and are spreading across the world faster than previous waves of technological innovation.” (Wermelinger, 2016).

Within this ecosystem rose the gig-economy or “sharing” economy. As defined by the UK government, it “involves the exchange of labour for money between individuals or companies via digital platforms that actively facilitate matching between providers and customers, on a short-term and payment-by-task basis,” (The Gig Economy: What Is It, Why Is It in the Headlines and What Does the Future Hold?, 2023). This new type of business model disrupts the traditional corporate-centered industries and instead leans toward a “peer-to-peer commercial exchange”. (Sundararajan, 2016).

The Philippines is no stranger to this economy. For instance, the mobile shopping platform Shopee, which was initially launched in 2015, has more than 6 million downloads, and over 3 million active listings by over 200,000 sellers in just three (3) years’ time. (Times, 2018). When the COVID-19 outbreak plagued the country in 2020, the country’s unemployment rate rose to 17.7%, which is equal to approximately 7.3 million Filipinos. Hence, to cope, one of the alternative options Filipinos pursued is online selling. According to data from Rappler, over 75,000 online businesses registered during the pandemic (Rappler, 2023). Shopee, on the other hand, provided aid through the “Shopee Sellers Education Hub”. This is a free online sub-platform that aimed to guide both prospective and newly registered sellers in setting up their pages, facilitating documentary requirements, and promoting their businesses among others. (Seller Education Hub, n.d.). At present, online platforms such as Lazada, GCash and Grab are other examples that continue to be utilized by Filipinos both for the flexibility, convenience and/or income opportunities they offer.

Bureaucratic Efficiency

Digitalization, in the context of the strategic thrusts of each administration, is often focused on two (2) aspects: Spurring greater economic opportunities and improving bureaucracy. These are evident within the past three administrations, from the Aquino III administration to the Marcos Jr. administration.

One of the commitments under the Aquino administration is promoting ease in doing business. As such, in October 2010, the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) launched the electronic business name registration system (eBNRS), one of the

agency's "anti-red tape initiatives in line with the government's policy of streamlining the bureaucratic processes and curbing corruption in the frontline agencies." (Remo, 2015).

The result of this is the significant reduction of applying for a business name, with the process shortened to 15 minutes through a 1-page application form and signature. Moreover, entrepreneurs and businesses can have their DTI business name registration certificate in less than 30 minutes. (Villamejor-Mendoza et al., 2018). Two years after, the Philippine Business Registry (PBR) was launched. It integrated the eBNRS with other line agencies, such as the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR), Social Security System (SSS), Home Mutual Development Fund, Philippine Health Insurance Corp. (PhilHealth), and Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) (Remo, 2015), serving as a one-stop shop for entrepreneurs and businesses. Finally, this was capped by the introduction of the electronic payment (ePayment) scheme wherein fees can be paid through mobile devices and or computer.

The same agenda was carried by his successor, former President Rodrigo R. Duterte. While the Duterte administration is often associated with its two major agenda, namely the War on Drugs and the Build, Build, Build Program, it also pursued bureaucratic efficiency through digitalization. On, 14 October 2016, then-President Duterte signed Executive Order No. 06, "Institutionalizing the 8888 Citizens' Complaint Hotline and Establishing the 8888 Citizens' Complaint Center". (Executive Order No. 06, 2016). Said hotline provided a platform for the public to report their complaints and or grievances against government agencies, officials, and or employees.

Moreover, as premised earlier, on 22 May 2018, Republic Act No. 11032 otherwise known as the "Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018" was signed into law. Said RA aimed to streamline [then] current systems and procedures on government services. (Republic Act 11032, 2018). It is ought to be a realization of Point #3 of the 10-Point Socio-Economic Agenda of the Duterte, which is to "Increase competitiveness and the ease of doing business." (GMA News, 2016).

The Fiscal Year (FY) 2023 National Budget is the first full-year budget under the Marcos Jr. administration. A total amount of PHP 5.268 trillion was allotted, guided by the virtue of fiscal responsibility and accountability. The administration remains committed in accelerating recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic while simultaneously aiming in protecting the Filipino people's purchasing power (President Marcos Jr. Signs Historic 2023 National Budget Into Law, n.d.).

Similar to his predecessors, the Marcos Jr. administration's 8-point Socio-economic Agenda espouses the pursuit of digitalization through Agenda 8: Bureaucratic Efficiency. Boasting a total budget of PhP 15.6 billion, it was geared towards efforts "to digitalize government process and operations." (GAA 2023 Starting Point for Marcos Jr. Administration's 8-Point Socioeconomic Agenda, n.d.). This is in line with the thrust for a lean, efficient, and responsive government workforce.

The e-Government Philippines, or simply referred to as eGov PH, is a mobile application that “simplifies transactions between the government and citizens”. (EGOVPH, n.d.). Also referred to as the “super app”, eGov PH serves as the backbone of digitalization efforts in Marcos administration towards the pursuit for global competitiveness. Said app is a one-stop shop wherein users can gather information as well as transact to various agencies such as GSIS, SSS and PhilHealth at the convenience of their mobile devices. In addition to regular internet and mobile devices users in the metro, this application is being gradually pushed among Filipinos in isolated areas with the goal of providing greater connectivity and access.

This endeavour is also in alignment by the agenda of ease of doing business that was pursued by Marcos Jr.’s predecessors, reducing and red tape and enhancing overall user experience. Moreover, it is bound to significantly impact the lives of Filipinos, especially those who may not have access to physical government offices or find it difficult navigating through a bureaucratic maze.

However, it is important to note that several factors may influence whether these digitalization initiatives will succeed or fail, including proper budget implementation, adaptability of government institutions to digital services, and acceptance by citizens. For instance, while rolling out the eGov PH Mobile Application, the government needs to train its employees adequately, raise awareness among members of the public and find ways of bridging the gap between people who can afford digital gadgets and those who cannot particularly among minority races (marginalized and underserved communities).

Consequently, privacy and security concerns must take precedence in implementing any form of electronic service provision by governments. Given this ever-increasing personal identifiable information being captured and processed via platforms like eGov PH Mobile Application necessitates the establishment strong data protection measures along with protocols thus preserving citizen’s rights as well as maintaining trust given to them for their welfare by Filipinos from online state operations.

Convergence

Perhaps the quintessential example of convergence between GAD and Digitalization in the Philippines is the creation of the Gender Mainstreaming Monitoring System (GMMS). Developed in 2014, the GMMS serves as an “e-portal to track the gender mainstreaming initiatives of government agencies at various levels”. (Philippine Commission on Women, 2023).

The GMMS provides government agencies the platform to enter data on their GAD policies and interventions, monitor progress real-time, and overall facilitate compliance with respect to their approved GAD Plans and Budget (GPB). Moreover, the GMMS also acts as a knowledge management system that enables the sharing of insights and best practices associated with GAD among different agencies (Philippine Commission on Women, 2023). This functionality fosters collaboration between

governmental organizations through learning that causes change for better concerning gender mainstreaming.

The development and implementation of the GMMS signify that Philippine's government is committed to employing digital technologies for further advancement towards gender equality and women empowerment. By digitalizing GAD monitoring-reporting mechanisms, collection of data by GMMS becomes well-ordered. This facilitates the analysis and dissemination of said data and allows policy makers and stakeholders to make evidence-based decisions, thereby designing more effective interventions. (Illo et al., 2010). Furthermore, the GMMS aligns with broader national efforts towards e-governance promotion and public sector digitization by the government. The Philippine Digital Strategy puts emphasis on "enhancing the capability of government structures and institutions as well as upgrading the ICT skills of the entire bureaucracy." (Philippine Digital Strategy, 2014).

Even though it is an important step forward in monitoring and evaluation of gender mainstreaming efforts, GMMS should not merely focus on data collection and reporting alone when aiming at achieving gender equality. the GMMS should be harnessed to further bridge the gap between citizens and government agencies, particularly where GAD efforts are concerned. In an age where technology continues to shape society and internal administrative processes as a whole, it is important to utilize available technological options so that any initiative geared towards the betterment of citizens is streamlined and free of any internal and external difficulties. This will reduce instances where people, particularly vulnerable groups such as women and children, are unable to join the government as it spearheads projects and plans for their safety and development.

To summarize, the GMMS encapsulates the convergence of GAD mainstreaming and digitalization efforts in the Philippines. It helps in promoting and advancing the use of digital technologies both on a personal and governmental scale. At the same time, it can also help government agencies in expediting their planning and execution of GAD initiatives by providing them with avenues to store, analyse, compare, and process the data stemming from the results of their efforts. In turn, this can help them launch better projects and implement more effective interventions for vulnerable groups.

Complementary to the GMMS is the establishment of the GAD Corner. As described by the Commission on Filipinos Overseas (CFO), "it is the [CFO's] collection of GAD knowledge materials and its related programs, projects and activities. It serves as a portal for accessing and sharing information on mainstreaming gender and development." (Gender and Development Corner, n.d.). National Agencies, such as the DILG, DSWD and DPWH to name a few have integrated an online GAD corner to their respective official websites, allowing its stakeholders and the general public easier access.

However, this is all dependent on whether the government agencies are committed enough as well as having an understanding on how they can use it, hence

integrating gender perspective into their policies and programs or not. In future, there must be a comprehensive strategy to address all forms of gender disparities while exploiting digital tools to that effect.

Conclusions

It is established that Gender Mainstreaming and Digitalization are consciously being prioritized and sustained across administrations in the Philippines. However, it is also evident that the execution of these initiatives is anchored on different priorities. Digitalization efforts are centered on promoting bureaucratic efficiencies, improved connectivity and stimulating economic activity.

On the other hand, GAD mainstreaming focuses on the issuance of policies that promote gender sensitivity, inclusivity, protection, and capacity building. This is very evident in the numerous issuances and development plans from Presidential Decree No. 633 to RA 9710.

While the convergence of these two efforts has taken place, such as the implementation of the GMMS and GAD Corner, reviewed literature suggests that it is still not greatly emphasized on and convergent efforts are more agency-specific rather than a collective conscious effort. This current state or limitation can be transformed as an avenue for improvement and innovation.

Recommendations

As premised earlier, the Philippines' GAD mainstreaming and Digitalization efforts have been ingrained in the social fabric across administrations. This shows a clear sense of commitment and dedication to growth and development. However, greater convergence between these two equally efforts is essential if these are aspired to yield maximum results. This can be facilitated through the following:

Inclusive Policy and Program Integration – The government must ensure that today's technology integrates both GAD efforts and digitalization to readily bring its initiatives directly to its citizens. At the same time, it must continue to ensure the development of gender-responsive policies through inclusion that caters for specific needs and challenges faced by women as well as other marginalized groups seeking to access and benefit from digital technologies. (Gurumurthy & Chami, 2014).

Greater Accessibility and Capacity Building – The government should facilitate greater accessibility on both GAD and Digitalization efforts. Complement access with capacity building for civil servants, non-governmental organizations, and the general public – especially those from the vulnerable sectors to enable them gain relevant skills on how to maximize ICTs in promoting GAD as well as addressing gender related issues. (Hernandez & Roberts, 2018).

Robust Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) System – Another viable step would be to create a comprehensive MEAL system that tracks the progress, impact, and challenges of GAD and digitalization initiatives, promoting greater transparency, accountability, and continuous learning. (EvalCommunity, 2024).

The Philippine government can continue reaching out its citizens better by remaining adaptive innovative and sustainable. Ultimately, this is aimed at achieving a digitally literate society that puts gender at its core while ensuring equal access of benefits that come with digitization regardless of one's geographical location and socio-economic status.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As part of the ethical standards of conducting research, the researchers have exercised due diligence in the proper citation of literature used as well as ensuring that both physical and online copies were sourced only from reputable sources. Moreover, to avoid plagiarism, the researchers subjected the manuscript to multiple iterations of proofreading and internal vetting. Finally, as stated in the abstract and methodology, the analysis and recommendations will be based primarily on the analysis of the literature cited and done purely for academic purposes.

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to express their sincerest gratitude and profound respect to Professors Marjorie R. Rola PhD, Jasmin D. Niguidula PhD, Jonathan M. Caballero PhD and Mr. Raymond Jay L. Mazo for their invaluable insights on the structuring and cohesion of narratives. Moreover, the researchers would like to thank Mr. Franco Inno Pineda, for lending his expertise in proofreading the manuscript prior to its submission.

REFERENCES

- 1987 Philippine Constitution, Article II, Section 14.
1987 Philippine Constitution, Article II, Section 24.
Aliliran, K. (2022, August 25). Presidential Decree No. 633: Creating the National Commission on the Role of Filipino Women. Philippine Commission on Women.
<https://pcw.gov.ph/presidential-decree-no-633-creating-the-national-commission-on-the-role-of-filipino-women/>
Bhandari, P. (2023, June 22). What Is Qualitative research? Methods & Examples. Scribbr.
<https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/qualitative-research/>
Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
Bukht, R., & Heeks, R. (2017). Defining, conceptualising and measuring the digital economy. *Social Science Research Network*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3431732>
Bumann, J., & Peter, M. (2019). Action Fields of Digital Transformation - A Review and Comparative Analysis of Digital Transformation Maturity Models and Frameworks. In

- Digitalisierung und andere Innovationsformen im Management (pp. 13–40). Edition Gesowip.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337167323_Action_Fields_of_Digital_Transformation_-_A_Review_and_Comparative_Analysis_of_Digital_Transformation_Maturity_Models_and_Frameworks
- Content Analysis Method and Examples | Columbia Public Health. (2023, March 30). Columbia University Mailman School of Public Health.
<https://www.publichealth.columbia.edu/research/population-health-methods/content-analysis>
- Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) for Youth. (2013, May 1). UN Women – Headquarters. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2016/12/cedaw-for-youth#:~:text=The%20Convention%20on%20the%20Elimination,women's%20and%20girls'%20equal%20rights.>
- convergence. (2024). In Merriam-Webster Dictionary. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/convergence>
- Crismundo, K. (2021, April 26). Gov't accelerates digitalization of services. Philippine News Agency. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1138083>
- Dictionary.com | Meanings & Definitions of English Words. (2020). In Dictionary.com. <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/efficiency>
- EGOVPH. (n.d.). eGovPH. https://e.gov.ph/?fbclid=IwAR1nI2fhX-zaSDGVd2h_QBnEpVkTxm56mNkqtijcCoHolyB1mHCNt0YVF3k
- EvalCommunity. (2024, June 21). Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) - EvalCommunity. <https://www.evalcommunity.com/career-center/meal/#:~:text=MEAL%20provides%20a%20structured%20approach,%2C%20implementation%2C%20and%20resource%20allocation.>
- Executive Order No. 322, s.1971.
- Executive Order No. 348, s.1989.
- Executive Order No. 273, s.1995.
- Executive Order No. 06, s.2016.
- Fourth World Conference on Women, Beijing 1995. (n.d.).
<https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/beijing/platform/plat1.htm>
- GAA 2023 starting point for Marcos Jr. administration's 8-Point Socioeconomic Agenda. (n.d.). <https://www.dbm.gov.ph/index.php/management-2/360-gaa-2023-starting-point-for-marcos-jr-administrations-8-point-socioeconomic-agenda>
- Gender and Development Corner. (n.d.). Commission on Filipinos Overseas. Retrieved June 28, 2024, from <https://cfo.gov.ph/gender-and-development-gad-corner/#:~:text=The%20consolidation%20of%20the%20reference,gender%20concepts%20across%20all%20sectors.>
- GMA News. (2016, June 20). Duterte's economic team reveals 10-point socioeconomic agenda. GMA News Online.
<https://www.gmanetwork.com/news/money/economy/570703/duterte-s-economic-team-reveals-10-point-socioeconomic-agenda/story/>
- Gurumurthy, A., & Chami, N. (2014). Gender equality in the information society -a review of current literature and recommendations for policy and practice. ResearchGate.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/297737616_Gender_equality_in_the_information_society_-_a_review_of_current_literature_and_recommendations_for_policy_and_practice
- Gurumurthy, A., Chami, N., McConchie, J., Kelly, S., Deo, R., Macapagal, M., Peralta, M., & Kim, J. (2016). E-Government for Women's Empowerment in Asia and the Pacific. In

- ESCAP (Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific). United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific.
<https://www.unescap.org/sites/default/files/E-Government-for-Women-in-Asia-Pacific.pdf>
- Hernandez, K., & Roberts, T. (2018). Leaving No One Behind in a Digital World. In GOV.UK. UK Government's Department for International Development (DFID).
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5c178371ed915d0b8a31a404/Emerging_Issues_LNOBDW_final.pdf
- Ilo, J., Encinas-Franco, J., Villaseñor, J., Leyesa, M., & De Los Trino, F. (2010). ACCOUNTING FOR GENDER RESULTS: A Review of the Philippine GAD Budget Policy [Miriam College - Women and Gender Institute]. https://www.treasury.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/AFGR_Book.pdf
- Making government work for women's empowerment and gender equity. (2000, June).
<https://library.pcw.gov.ph/making-government-work-for-womens-empowerment-and-gender-equity/>
- McCombes, S. (2023, June 22). Descriptive Research | Definition, Types, Methods & Examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- National Computer Center & National IT Industry Promotion Agency. (2012, December). Electronic Government Development & Strategy [Press release].
https://www.dbm.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/MITHI/Philippines%20E-GovMasterPlan_%28final%20draft%29.pdf
- National Economic Development Authority. (2023). PHILIPPINE DEVELOPMENT PLAN 2023-2028 [Press release]. <https://pdp.neda.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/PDP-2023-2028.pdf>
- National Information Technology Plan for the 21st Century (IT21). (n.d.). <https://serp-p.pids.gov.ph/publication/public/view?slug=national-information-technology-plan-for-the-21st-century-it21>
- Philippine Commission on Women. (2023, October 12). Gender Mainstreaming Monitoring System - Philippine Commission on Women. <https://pcw.gov.ph/gender-mainstreaming-monitoring-system/>
- Philippine Digital Strategy. (2014, June 18). Department of Information and Communications Technology. <https://dict.gov.ph/philippine-digital-strategy/>
- Presidential Decree No. 633, s.1975.
- President Marcos Jr. Signs Historic 2023 National Budget into Law. (n.d.).
<https://www.dbm.gov.ph/index.php/management-2/363-president-marcos-jr-signs-historic-2023-national-budget-into-law>
- Rappler. (2023, May 19). Shopee in the pandemic: Helping Filipino entrepreneurs and communities. RAPPLER. <https://www.rappler.com/brandrap/goodrap/shopee-helping-filipino-entrepreneurs-communities-covid-19-pandemic/>
- Remo, A. (2015, July 25). Sona promises: Has Aquino improved ease of doing business? INQUIRER.NET. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/707710/sona-promises-has-aquino-improved-ease-of-doing-business>
- Republic Act No. 11032, 2018.
- Republic Act No. 9710, 2009.
- Rockman, B. (1998, July 20). Bureaucracy | Definition, Characteristics, Examples, & Facts. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/bureaucracy>
- Rouse, M. (Ed.). (2023, September 20). Convergence. Technopedia. Retrieved June 20, 2024, from <https://www.techopedia.com/definition/769/convergence>
- Seller Education Hub. (n.d.). <https://seller.shopee.ph/edu/home>
- Sundararajan, A. (2016). The sharing economy: the end of employment and the rise of Crowd-Based capitalism. <https://econpapers.repec.org/bookchap/mtptitles/0262034573.htm>

- The gig economy: what is it, why is it in the headlines and what does the future hold? (2023, May 1). World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/05/what-gig-economy-workers/>
- gigTimes, M. (2018, February 10). Shopee PH's 'mobile-first' approach key to e-commerce success. The Manila Times. <https://www.manilatimes.net/2018/02/11/business/shopee-phs-mobile-first-approach-key-e-commerce-success/379508>
- Villamejor-Mendoza, M., Baylon, M., Cuaresma, J., Diola, M., Florano, E., & Sobrapeña, A. (2018). The Performance of the Aquino Administration (2010-2016): An Assessment. In UP-NCPAG. University of the Philippines Diliman - National College of Public Administration and Governance. <https://ncpag.upd.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/PerfromanceOfAqunioAdmin.pdf>
- Wermelinger, C. D. & S. M. & M. (2016). Harnessing the digital economy for developing countries. ideas.repec.org. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/oec/devaaa/334-en.html>
- What is gender mainstreaming? - Gender Equality - www.coe.int. (n.d.). Gender Equality. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/genderequality/what-is-gender-mainstreaming>